

IPBES Nexus Assessment

Chapter 5, data management report 2 – Governance figures

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Description

Response options in each Chapter 5 subchapter (i.e., biodiversity, water, food, health, climate change) were assessed within the context of nexus governance considerations based on policy instrument typologies, actor typologies, and enablers and barriers identified in Chapter 4 of the assessment. The purposes of this assessment were to 1) classify response options as policy instruments, 2) identify key actors and their roles for each response option and 3) identify enablers of and barriers to successful response option implementation. The Chapter 4 typologies are:

Response option classification

Action or management

Policy instrument (see policy instrument typologies below)

Enabler (see enablers and barriers below)

Policy instrument typologies (Chapter 4, Table 4.4)

Economic and financial

Legal and regulatory

Social and cultural

Rights-based and customary

Actors and actor typologies (Chapter 4, section 4.3.4)

Actors

Global and regional institutions

National governments

Local governments and municipalities

Knowledge and educational communities

Civil society organizations

Community-based organizations

Indigenous Peoples and local communities

Private sector and business organizations

Science-policy interfaces

Financing institutions

Media and the arts

Actor typologies

Influencer
Affected
Key player

Enablers and barriers (Chapter 4, Table 4.6)

Policy design and implementation
Equity and diversity
Institutional capacity
Finance and economics
Behaviour and lifestyle
Technology
Material endowments

Process overview

Based on the response option scores (Chapter 5, data management report 1) and author expertise, each Chapter 5 subchapter team assessed the response options within the context of nexus governance as follows:

Response option classification

Each response option was classified as 1) an action or management, 2) policy instrument, and/or an enabler. Response options classified as policy instruments were further categorized based on the policy instrument typologies listed above in the Description section.

The classifications are visualized in the following figures:

Chapter 5.1, Figure 5.1.10
Chapter 5.2, Figure 5.2.7
Chapter 5.3, Figure 5.3.17
Chapter 5.4, Figure 5.4.13
Chapter 5.5, Figure 5.5.14

Actor involvement in response options

For each response option, the enablers and barriers listed above in the Description section were categorized based on the strength to which they enable or serve as a barrier to response option implementation: strong enabler, enabler, both an enabler and barrier, barrier, strong barrier. Enablers and barriers could also be categorized as “unclear” or “no data/unable to determine”.

Actor involvement in response options is visualized in the following figures:

Chapter 5.1, Figure 5.1.12
Chapter 5.2, Figure 5.2.6
Chapter 5.3, Figure 5.3.18
Chapter 5.4, Figure 5.4.15
Chapter 5.5, Figure 5.5.13

Enablers and barriers

For each response option, the enablers and barriers listed above in the Description section were categorized based on the strength to which they enable or serve as a barrier to response option implementation: strong enabler, enabler, both an enabler and barrier, barrier, strong barrier. Enablers and barriers could also be categorized as “unclear” or “no data/unable to determine”.

Response option enablers and barriers are visualized in the following figures:

Chapter 5.1, Figure 5.1.11

Chapter 5.2, Figure 5.2.8

Chapter 5.3, Figure 5.3.19

Chapter 5.4, Figure 5.4.14

Chapter 5.5, Figure 5.5.15

Chapter 5.6, Supplementary material 5.6.1

In addition, the enabler and barrier categorizations were pooled across the subchapters 5.1 to 5.5 to provide an overall assessment of how many response options each enabler and barrier affects. The pooled categorizations are visualized in Chapter 5.6, Figure 5.6.6. To account for the combining of 8 response options into 4 sets of response options based on IPBES 11 negotiations (i.e., B03/C11, Agroecology; F11/C15, Sustainable healthy diets; F03/C02, Sustainable intensification; B02/C14, Urban nature-based solutions), which gives a total of 71 response options as presented in the Summary for Policymakers and Chapter 5.6, the response option count for a given enabler/barrier category (e.g., policy design and implementation) and enabler/barrier type (e.g., strong enabler), was reduced by 1 for each set of combined response options in cases where the same enabler/barrier type was selected for the individual response options within a given set. For example:

Enabler/barrier category: policy design and implementation

Chapter enabler/barrier designation:

B03, Agroecology: strong enabler

C11, Agroecology: strong enabler

Response option count adjustment for strong enabler type: subtract 1 to account for duplicate

F11, Sustainable healthy diets: strong enabler

C02, Sustainable healthy diets: strong enabler

Response option count adjustment for strong enabler type: subtract 1 to account for duplicate

B02, Urban nature-based solutions: strong enabler

C14, Urban nature-based solutions: strong enabler

Response option count adjustment for strong enabler type: subtract 1 to account for duplicate

Total to subtract: 3

Number of response options for which policy design and implementation is a strong enabler, based on the original, full set of 75 response options assessed: 56

Number of response options for which policy design and implementation is a strong enabler, based on 71 response options assessed and accounting for the combined response options: $56 - 3 = 53$

Note that accounting for the combined response options did not change the design of Figure 5.5.6. That is, the dots sizes in Figure 5.5.6 are the same when visualizing how many response options each enabler and barrier affects based on either 75 response options or 71 response options.

Files attached

ID	File name	File type	File size	Description
A	v1.0.0_IPBES_NXS_ch 5.1_governance tables_A	.xlsx	30 KB	Workbook of three governance tables for Chapter 5.1: 1) response option classification, 2) actors, 3) enablers and barriers
B	v1.0.0_IPBES_NXS_ch 5.2_governance tables_B	.xlsx	30 KB	Workbook of three governance tables for Chapter 5.2: 1) response option classification, 2) actors, 3) enablers and barriers
C	v1.0.0_IPBES_NXS_ch 5.3_governance tables_C	.xlsx	30 KB	Workbook of three governance tables for Chapter 5.3: 1) response option classification, 2) actors, 3) enablers and barriers
D	v1.0.0_IPBES_NXS_ch 5.4_governance tables_D	.xlsx	30 KB	Workbook of three governance tables for Chapter 5.4: 1) response option classification, 2) actors, 3) enablers and barriers
E	v1.0.0_IPBES_NXS_ch 5.5_governance tables_E	.xlsx	24 KB	Workbook of three governance tables chapter 5.5: 1) response option classification, 2) actors, 3) enablers and barriers
F	v1.0.0_IPBES_NXS_ch 5.6_enablers_barriers_F	.xlsx	21 KB	Response options enablers and barriers table for Chapter 5.6